

THE ISSUES OF TEACHING UZBEK STUDENTS ENGLISH

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Annotation: This thesis discusses the issues of teaching English in Uzbekistan and its methods, as well as tips for teaching effectiveness. It also highlights the importance of moving from a teacher-centered approach to teaching and learning English, and presents the results of an educational test aimed at creating a student-centered environment in the dialect classroom.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisda O'zbekistonda ingliz tilini o'rgatish masalalari va uning usullari, shuningdek, o'qitish samaradorligi bo'yicha maslahatlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, u ingliz tilini o'qitish va o'rganishda o'qituvchiga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvdan o'tish muhimligini ta'kidlaydi va dialekt sinfida o'quvchiga yo'naltirilgan muhit yaratishga qaratilgan ta'lim testi natijalarini taqdim etadi.

В данной диссертации рассматриваются вопросы преподавания английского языка в Узбекистане и его методы, а также советы по эффективности преподавания. В нем также подчеркивается важность перехода от подхода, ориентированного на преподавателя, к преподаванию и изучению английского языка, и представлены результаты образовательного теста, направленного на создание лично-ориентированной среды в диалектном классе.

Keywords: non-native-English-speaking teachers, teacher-centered teaching, student-centered teaching.

Multifaceted contacts, correspondence and trust have become a necessary part of the advanced world, opening incredibly open doors for speakers of dialects usually perceived as lingua francas.

English has acquired the status of the "world language" used for worldwide intercession over the past many years. Approximately 400 million people communicate in English as their first language, and estimates of the number of non-native English speakers range from 470 million to over a billion, depending on the value of education or language ability. The current exams confirm that "the number of students learning English is increasing and the age is decreasing", and the growing prominence of the English language on the planet "has become one of the few exceptional ways to cope with the realities of

modern life around the world." one]. According to the Euronews television channel, in 2008 approximately 56% of Europeans were bilingual, and 38% of them communicated in English [2]. The Russian diary Kommersant-Vlast noted that 98% of German physicists and 83% of German scientists distribute their logical papers only in English [3]. Experts expect that by 2020, 30-35% of the Asian population (compared to the current 8-10%) will use English consistently. Another vivid illustration of the consistently growing popularity of the English language in Asian countries is the appearance of the expression "Asian native English speakers" [4].

A 2024 UNESCO report [5] showed that only 43.1% of the Uzbek population communicates in a foreign language as a follow-up language. [6].

This requires updating and creating English language teaching methodologies that enable non-local speakers to gain adequate English-speaking skills in order to enter the growing circle of the Kachru model [7].

In the English language display industry, which has recently grown into a worldwide enterprise, the majority of teachers in general are non-native English speakers. As you might expect, over the past many years, the polarity between Native English Teachers (NEST) and Non-Native English Teachers (NNEST) has generated a lot of thought, discussion and conversation. The focus of this conversation has shifted little by little from thinking about local speakers (NS) as the main solid source of etymological information and the ability to recommend terms, such as "gifted language client" [8] or "experienced speaker" [8]. 9], finally, the conclusion that local speakers of a non-local language can get "instinct, sentence structure, suddenness, innovation, control over common sense and the nature of the translation of "ordinary" local speakers" [10].

While a few significant advances have been taken to further develop English language learning in Uzbekistan, the development of the gaining climate and the shift from educator focused to understudy focused training are not quick cycles. Electronic instructing and learning strategies and procedures are increasingly more frequently included into the educational plan, while the job of current gadgets, for example, advanced cameras and PDA cameras is by all accounts misjudged. These contraptions are a vital piece of numerous youthful people's lives these days, and our perceptions propose that they animate students' useful relational abilities, while the Internet is regularly seen by them just as the wellspring of data.

Notwithstanding, research-based proof that making video films in the ESL study halls can spur students, urge and empower them to involve English in a

more normal manner, and therefore upgrade their English relational abilities is extremely scant. Our review makes a stride towards evaluating the adequacy of students' filmmaking as an English language learning apparatus. It ought to be noticed that Uzbek EFL instructors additionally face numerous expert difficulties, the primary of them being the strength of conventional educator focused techniques in language study halls. Whenever an instructor is put at the focal point of the learning system, the person in question fills in as the fundamental wellspring of semantic and social data for students, as well as their vitally phonetic good example. We have accepted that such methodology limits students' learning open doors, yet additionally puts extra strain on an instructor.

Our discoveries revealed that native-speaker instructors highlight Uzbek while communicating in English, which connected with their dialect capability and working experience, and couldn't be totally disposed of. It made sense of why outside regular dialect climate, instructors frequently neglect to assess the level of their articulation because of goal reasons, like absence of scholastic situation in far off nations, restricted correspondence with unfamiliar friends, and solid impact of their local language. This inflection is therefore imitated by the students who in the greater part of the cases see their EFL instructor as the main semantic good example and placed a lot of validity into them. This outcome experiencing the same thing when educators can't diminish their students' complement, since this is their own inflection precisely imitated by the students.

Moreover, we noticed that the observed teachers behaved formally in the classroom, preferred to use ordinary teaching materials, bombarded students with school assignments, and the atmosphere in their illustrations was generally annoying to the point of creating obstacles for correspondence between students. This urged us to look for new EFL showing strategies, with the goal that we could relieve the effect of NNESTs' phonetic highlight on students' articulation, put understudy at the focal point of the learning system and establish more advantageous and solid homeroom climate. Additionally, we attempted to utilize video materials and introduced films, as well as students' and teachers' self-assessments showed that leading examination through filmmaking can be viewed as a powerful and imaginative instructing strategy.

This strategy proved beneficial to both students and teachers as it worked on the viability of the demonstration process, inspired students, and provided them with the opportunity to develop related interdisciplinary skills:

1. capacity to involve fitting dialect in talking and composing for creating a film on the picked theme;
2. economical discussion abilities, including capacity to underwrite a discussion with numerous talk members;
3. capacity to utilize various types of perusing (skimming, examining, serious, broad, and so on) and to separate explicit data from enormous texts;
4. capacity to dissect message structure (separate between sections, recognize theme sentences, decide the creator's perspective);
5. capacity to freely make texts of various sorts, points and subjects, utilizing portrayal, portrayal, thinking and argumentation relying on the reason for correspondence;
6. diverse relational abilities, created by raising social mindfulness and the increment of semantic and social information;
7. the ability to use knowledge of a foreign language to form a more tolerant attitude towards the culture, history and modern problems of other nations, understanding the importance of learning other languages and developing readiness to use knowledge of a foreign language for cross-border and intercultural cooperation.

Our simple survey revealed a correlation between students' English proficiency and their willingness to participate: the strongest students expressed a negative attitude towards filmmaking and preferred to stick to standard teaching methods and exam tasks, such as questions and answers, discussions with the teacher, presentations and role-playing games. However, after completing the video project, the vast majority of students recognized that this form of work has many advantages and merits. Teachers were also very enthusiastic about video filming, pointing to the following important qualities of this type of work: the ability to stimulate students' interest in learning a foreign language, develop their intellectual abilities, encourage independent thinking and develop critical skills. as well as their self-discipline and ability to learn on their own. Weaknesses noted by the teachers included a lack of computer-aided film editing skills, clear assessment criteria, and written instructions for teaching. In most Uzbek educational institutions, teaching foreign languages is traditionally carried out by creating a special artificial bilingual learning environment, i.e. using a complex of "pre-planned activities, strictly controlled and controlled" [9]. However, the possibility of developing bilingualism outside the natural language environment causes heated debate among Uzbek specialists in the methodology of teaching foreign languages. So, they mainly

receive information about this non-native language and foreign-language culture from their Uzbek-speaking teachers, who, in turn, are strongly influenced by their native (Uzbek) language and very often explore foreign-language culture indirectly, like their students - through scientific literature, textbooks and media.

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